

TABLE 1 and Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 describe the requirements, concepts and processes, respectively, for the **Text Messaging** problem (FP1)

TABLE 1

ITEMS DEFINING THE FAMILIAR PROBLEM FP1

TYPE	ITEM ID	DESCRIPTION
Requirements	R1	Users will be able to connect to the chat server by entering an ID and password.
	R2	The ID and password will be created via a web page.
	R3	If the ID and password are incorrect, the system will display a message.
	R4	After the system has correctly connected to the server (internal company network), it will wait for user input or reception of a chat message.
	R5	The system will be able to run in both the foreground and background. The system will provide the option to:
	R6	Select the chat/contact in/with which users wish to communicate (Select contact).
	R7	Write a message.
	R8	The application will only send plain text messages. (Images, icons, multimedia messages, etc., will not be included.) There is no limit on the size (number of characters) per message.
	R9	Use a user ID/email address to enter contact.
	R10	Specify user ID to delete contact.
	R11	Accept an entry request.
	R12	Reject an entry request.
	R13	Send a message.
	R14	Messages will be sent between two users only.
	R15	The system will request explicit confirmation from users before sending messages/ requests to server.
	R16	A chat selected by the user will open and display all the unread messages.
	R17	Unread messages will be highlighted in bold.
	R18	The system will display a message log according to the following parameters or options: 1. Last hour or 2. Last four messages.
	R19	If the system is running in the background: A pop-up will notify users that a message has been received (depending on the operating system).
	R20	The message will be added to the respective chat, and an unread messages counter will be updated.
	R21	The notification will be added to the respective chat, and an unread messages counter will be updated.
	R22	The pop-up will be accompanied by a sound.
	R23	If the system is running in the foreground: If the message/notification is for the current chat, the message/notification will be displayed directly.
	R24	The date and time will be displayed together with the message/notification.
	R25	Otherwise, the message/notification will be added to the respective chat, and an unread messages/notifications counter will be updated, BUT the user will not be notified (as in the iPhone).
	R26	For delete notifications, both the input and the contact will be deleted immediately.
	R27	Users will be able to disconnect the chat server.
	R28	When the system receives a message/notification from the server, the following actions will be taken: (only if the program is running; otherwise, the messages will be lost).

TYPE	ITEM ID	DESCRIPTION
Concepts	C1	User
	C2	Contacts
	C3	Messages
	C4	Text
	C5	Chat
	C6	Entry request
	C7	Deletion request
	C8	Entry confirmation
	C9	Entry rejection
	C10	Log
Processes	A1	Connect to server
	A2	Wait for user input
	A3	Request contact entry
	A4	Accept entry request
	A5	Reject entry request
	A6	Request contact deletion
	A7	Select contact (chat)
	A8	Write message
	A9	Send message
	A10	Receive message
	A11	Send request
	A12	Receive request
	A13	Notify message reception
	A14	Execute deletion request
	A15	Close notification
	A16	Display message log (show message in chat)

FP1 – Activity Diagram

Fig. 1. Activity diagram for familiar problem – baseline experiment

FP1 - Concept Model

Fig. 2. Model of familiar problem concepts – baseline experiment

